

AI4

Status report on Quality Assurance and data FAIRness

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable describes the status of the WP7 activities since the first deliverable D7.1 [R1].

The work performed within the WP7 has been the coordination, design and implementation of:

1. The SW release process and procedures:
 - a. This procedure includes the guidelines of the Software and Services Quality Assurance.
2. The status of the FAIR assessment of the datasets.
3. The infrastructure deployment, integration and operation of the AI4EOSC platform and services.

These items have been discussed with the other WPs and described as live documents in Confluence Wiki pages.

The document is structured as follows.

- Section 2.: We describe the guidelines for the Software and Services Quality Assurance.
- Section 3.: Details the process and procedures for the SW release and the first release of the AI4OS stack.
- Section 4.: Describes the status of FAIR assessment of the datasets.
- Section 5.: Describes the architecture and deployment of the AI4EOSC platform infrastructure.
- Section 6.: We draw final remarks.

2. SOFTWARE AND SERVICES QUALITY ASSURANCE

The guidelines for the Software and Services QA, are detailed in the Confluence Wiki page:

- <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Software+and+Services+Quality+Assurance+%28SQA%29+guidelines>

Annex 1 reproduces these guidelines. They are largely based on the list described in the first deliverable D7.1 [R1], although with some changes that resulted from discussions with the developer teams in WP4 and WP5. As mentioned in the first deliverable D7.1, the criteria was taken from [R2]. They are divided into “**Mandatory**” and “**Optional**” criteria.

The “**Mandatory**” Quality Criteria is listed and explained next:

1. Code Accessibility [**QC.Acc**]: The source code is open and managed in a Version Control System (VCS), such as a Git repository.
2. Code Workflow [**QC.Wor**]: A change-based approach is accomplished with a branching model and a production branch maintains a working state of the Software.
3. Code Management [**QC.Man**]: Existence of an issue tracking system for structured software development. Track issues; new enhancements and defects (bugs, documentation typos, etc.).
4. Semantic Versioning [**QC.Ver**]: Specification for tagging the production releases.
5. Licensing [**QC.Lic**]: SW has an open source licence and this licence is hosted in the SW VCS repository.
6. Documentation [**QC.Doc**]: Documentation exists and is publicly available. The type of documents may depend on the type of SW. See details in Annex 1.
7. Delivery [**QC.Del**]: Comprises the build of Software into an artefact, its upload/registration into a public repository of such artefacts.
8. Deployment [**QC.Dep**]: Production-ready code can be deployed as a workable system with the minimal user or system administrator interaction leveraging Software Configuration Management (SCM) tools. The deployment of the several services developed within the project is described in section 5, this is the AI4EOC platform.

The “**Optional**” QA criteria are for the SW developer teams that aim at a badge awarded by EOSC-Synergy through the SQAaaS: <https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/>. There are three badges: Gold, Silver and Bronze.

For the Bronze badge additional documentation should be added to the VCS repository such as; contributing and code of conduct specifications.

For the Silver badge, SW source code should follow code styling (linting) standard rules and a metadata file for the SW (see details in Annex 1: Software and Services Quality Criteria).

For the Gold badge, SW source code should pass Static Application Security Testing (SAST).

3. SOFTWARE RELEASE, PROCESS AND PROCEDURES

The SW release of the AI4OS stack is a point in time release. This means that SW components are continuously developed and released following a DevOps approach with CI/CD Jenkins pipelines (c.f. deliverable D7.1 [R1]). As such, the latest version of a given SW component at the time of the planned AI4OS stack release, is the one to be part of it.

3.1 Process and procedures

The procedure for the AI4OS stack release is described in the Confluence Wiki:

- <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Software+Release+procedures>

The entities involved in the procedure are; the Software providers and the WP7 team. The procedure is as follows:

1. About 4 weeks before the planned release, open Jira tickets, for each SW component listed in the Confluence Wiki:
 - a. <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Software+and+Applications+information>
2. An SQAaaS assessment is performed for each SW component with the service <https://sqaaas.eosc-synergy.eu/>, a report is produced and attached to the corresponding ticket:
 - a. The report is produced in json and pdf formats, the json is used to parse the information in the report.
 - b. The Mandatory QA is inserted in the Jira ticket so that the SW developers can check, and eventually fix any failed criteria.
3. Upon the verification that all Mandatory criteria is passing, the Jira ticket can be closed and the SW component is considered fit for the release within the AI4os stack.
4. The last step is the announcement of the release in the AI4EOSC web pages and to the EOSC community.

3.2 First Software release

Following the information in the Confluence Wiki² and Deliverable D4.2 [R3] the list of components from WP4 that are part of the platform layer of the AI4OS stack to be included in the first release are the following:

SW component	Source code repository	Artifact repository	Version
PaaS Orchestrator	https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator-dashboard	https://hub.docker.com/r/indigodatacloud/orchestrator	3.2.1
PaaS Dashboard	https://github.com/indigo-dc/orchestrator-dashboard	https://hub.docker.com/r/indigodatacloud/orchestrator-dashboard	3.2.1
Infrastructure	https://github.com/gryca	https://hub.docker.com	1.15.0

² <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Software+and+Applications+information>

Manager (IM)	p/im	m/r/grycap/im	
OSCAR	https://github.com/grycap/oscar	https://hub.docker.com/r/grycap/oscar	3.0.0

Regarding the SW components from WP5 that are part of the service layer of the AI4OS stack (c.f. deliverable D5.2 [R4]), are the following:

SW component	Source code repository	Artifact repository	Version
AI4Compose	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose	N. A.	1.0.0
Platform API	https://github.com/AI4EOSC/ai4-papi	N. A.	1.0.0
AI4EOSC Dashboard	https://github.com/AI4EOSC/ai4-dashboard		1.5.0
Interactive Development Environment	https://github.com/deephdc/DEEP-OC-generic-dev	https://hub.docker.com/r/deephdc/deep-oc-generic-dev	2.1.3
Nomad + Consul + Traefik Ansible Roles	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-ansible		0.1.0
DEEPaaS	https://github.com/ai4os/DEEPaaS		2.2.0
Nomad tests	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-nomad_tests		0.1.0
Accounting	https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-accounting		1.0.0
MLflow server + Auth GUI	https://github.com/m-team-kit/mlflow-auth-gui		0.6.1
Frouros	https://github.com/IFCA-Advanced-Computing/frouros		0.7.1
Templates Hub	https://github.com/m-team-kit/cookiecutter-web	N. A.	1.0.0

The deliverables D4.2 from WP4 and D5.2 from WP5 have a detailed overview of all the features and fixes of the abovementioned components.

4. FAIR ASSESSMENT

Task 7.2 aims to support various use cases to ensure that different digital objects potentially reusable along the workflow adopt the FAIR principles. This task is scheduled to be carried out during the second half of the project, so this section describes the plan planning of the activities to be carried out rather than reporting the current status. Given the context where these use cases implement Machine Learning models, the initial step is to identify the different components in these workflows and evaluate how they can adopt the FAIR principles. One of the main objectives of the FAIR principles [R5] is not only to enhance the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data or digital objects but also to increase their transparency and reproducibility. This objective is closely linked to Task 5.4 concerning model provenance and domain metadata, which aims to establish a model provenance framework to describe all aspects of the AI/ML/DL models' provenance, including the identification of all components and their relationships.

Therefore, the FAIR assessment within AI4EOSC requires several steps to be genuinely useful for the use cases and to contribute to the concept of FAIR beyond datasets. The objective is to apply the concept of FAIR principles to the AI models and the completed workflow. To do so, the following steps will be followed:

- Firstly, considering exemplary use cases, the identification of components in the workflow must be conducted to ensure their reproducibility. This implies not only identifying the components themselves but also determining the type of relationships among them. Additionally, the appropriate approach must be selected, assessing the FAIRness of each component separately, the workflow itself, or both.
- Secondly, an analysis of the state of the art in the context of FAIR in Artificial Intelligence needs to be conducted, identifying which initiatives, programs, or forums are working on this topic.
- Finally, at the technical level, potential tools to ensure FAIRness along the workflow need to be selected, not only to evaluate the components but also to monitor and track for gathering sufficient information within the AI4EOSC platform.

4.1 Components to assess FAIRness

Thanks to the collaboration with Task 5.4, a list of components to track the actions performed during the AI models configuration, training, calibration and validation have been identified. This ensures the model provenance and the interaction

among components. This is closely linked to the concept of FAIR, as all components contributing to the creation of an AI model must be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and, especially, Reusable to ensure transparency and reproducibility. This begins with data, serving as input for the models, but extends beyond. Below is the list of identified components ensuring reproducibility and identifying the provenance of the models, along with characteristics that could make them FAIR:

- **Data:** Refers to the input data of the model, facilitating machine learning and potential output data with results. Both input and output data can come in various formats, depending on the type of machine learning model used or the implementation. To enhance their FAIRness, it is crucial to accurately identify them using persistent identifiers, establish their roles (training data, test data, validation data, results), make them accessible through standard protocols, and provide appropriate metadata. The datasets used by the models in the AI4EOSC catalogue will be published in open repositories that support the FAIR principles, trying to use formats that respect these principles.
- **Metadata:** Serves to document each component, offering information at descriptive, administrative, or structural levels. To enhance overall FAIRness, the appropriate metadata standard or format should be chosen, and semantic formats should be used to document the complete flow and relationship between components. The PROV-O [R6] ontological format, recommended by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [R7], serves as the starting point in this regard, thanks to the work of Task 5.4. In combination with PROV-O, the datasets used by the models in the AI4EOSC catalogue will be described with certain recommended metadata standards. In the case of multidisciplinary metadata, standard formats such as Dublin Core will be used, while for disciplinary data, the use of specific schemes for each use case will be suggested.
- **Settings and hyperparameters:** The configuration of a machine learning model and tuning of hyperparameters are crucial for enhancing model performance. Adopting FAIR principles ensures that these settings are transparent, accessible, and reusable across different research endeavours. Though not a component itself but part of the model, they should be exposed as part of the model metadata. MLflow will be used for the automatic capture of hyperparameters and included in the metadata. An MLflow service has already been deployed in the AI4EOSC platform, c.f. section 5.1.7.
- **Software:** Encompasses the model's implementation and all parts making it usable, including (re)training or inference. It may include preprocessing of data, results analysis, etc. It is important to note the list of requirements like libraries and their versions, as well as the computing environment where the software can be run. Apart from publishing the code in open repositories, the recommendations from FAIR for Research Software working Group at RDA will be taken into account.

- **Models:** Once the model is trained or even before, various components can be automatically packaged, such as weights or settings. Libraries such as Keras can save the model in HDF5 format, facilitating sharing and reuse for transfer learning. This package can be seen as the model itself, and this digital object will be also described by metadata.
- **Publications:** Model implementation often leads to scientific publications. It's important to track the results of model use adopting FAIR principles, for example, by publishing papers in trustworthy repositories.
- **Workflow:** the machine learning workflow represents all the steps followed in the process of the model creation and its use. This workflow needs to be published to adopt the FAIR principles, exposing the relationships among the components somehow, in a complete package or reflecting those interactions using a proper ontology. As will be explained in section 4.3.1, the workflows will be packaged following some system such as RO-Crates or Frictionless datasets.

This list of components serves as the starting point to ensure the entire machine learning model flow is FAIR. However, within the AI4EOSC context, its platform and use cases, a robust approach needs adoption, considering the state of the art and being supported by various technologies and tools to automate parts of the project and assess the FAIRness level.

4.2 State of the art: FAIRness for AI

One of its Interest Groups is the FAIR4ML RDA IG [R8], focused on applying the FAIR principles to machine learning tools and models. This group facilitates discussions among community members regarding the implementation of FAIR principles in the context of machine learning (ML). Recognizing that ML encompasses aspects of data, software, and computational workflows, the group acknowledges that direct application of FAIR principles to ML may not always be straightforward. Therefore, it seeks to identify domain-specific and domain-agnostic use cases to address gaps in existing FAIR principles as they relate to ML. To ensure relevance across various domains such as health, earth science, physics, agriculture, materials science, energy, and biology, the group may initiate individual task forces focused on specific domains. These task forces work in parallel on distinct topics to ensure comprehensive coverage of ML applications within different fields. While there are no outputs from this IG yet, AI4EOSC aims to actively participate in discussions during monthly meetings and RDA plenaries. The Interest Group is also connected to the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) WG, which produces results and organises activities related to the FAIRness of software components.

At the European level, various initiatives, projects, or infrastructures face similar challenges. EOSC-related projects like FAIR-Impact [R9] and FAIRCORE4EOSC [R10] aim to improve the level of FAIRness adoption within the European Open Science Cloud context. FAIR-IMPACT identifies practices, policies, tools, and

technical specifications toward a FAIR data management cycle, starting with real-life use cases in four different domains. Although the project is oriented to data, it is open to receiving new case studies to support the adoption and implementation of FAIR data principles. FAIRCORE4EOSC focuses on the development and realisation of core components for EOSC, related to Persistent Identifiers, connection of research entities supported by semantic technologies, or the development of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for improving interoperability. Both projects can contribute at different levels, both abstract and technical respectively, to the AI4EOSC objectives.

A first round of interactions has been established during the EOSC Winter School in January 2024, with the aim of finding potential synergies and adopting similar approaches within the projects.

In parallel, developments of ESFRIs like ELIXIR related to Machine Learning models and their reproducibility linked with FAIR principles are being taken into account. Aiming to select the best approach for AI4EOSC, we are in contact with researchers in ELIXIR working on the Machine Learning FAIRness topic. In summary, as part of this task, the current state of the various initiatives involved in applying the FAIR principles to Artificial Intelligence will be reviewed, and solutions as automatic as possible will be implemented for their deployment in the context of the AI4EOSC platform, benefiting from the developments and their various components.

4.3 Tools and Technologies

In order to ensure and assess the FAIRness of the digital object within the Machine Learning workflow, different tools and technologies need to be used to track and gather the required information, describe and document the workflow itself and to perform some metrics.

4.3.1 Data and Research Objects Packaging

In order to make machine learning workflows shareable, they need not only to be correctly documented and the relationships explicitly described, but also the different components need to be accessible. Just as the computing environment can be "packaged" in containers like Docker, there are different options to containerize data and research components into a single object that is easy to share, including not only data but also software components and metadata. Therefore, the components described in section 4.1 Components to assess FAIRness can benefit from using different approaches to be containerized. Since in many cases machine learning models require large amounts of input data for training, various models will be analysed, including the packaging of the complete dataset, packaging of exemplar data, or adding references to data published elsewhere. To support this action, at least two different ways of packaging

research components will be analysed: RO-Crates [R12] and Frictionless Data [R11].

RO-Crate, short for Research Object Crate, is a collaborative initiative aimed at providing a lightweight solution for bundling research data alongside their metadata. Utilising semantic technologies such as schema.org annotations in JSON-LD format, RO-Crate strives to democratise best practices in formal metadata description, catering to a broad spectrum of scenarios. Whether it is an individual researcher managing a folder of data or a large-scale computational research environment, RO-Crate seeks to streamline the process of packaging data with comprehensive metadata. Targeting a diverse audience encompassing researchers, digital repository managers, individual researchers seeking to enhance the FAIRness of their data, and data stewards supporting research projects, RO-Crate aims to serve as a versatile tool for enhancing data management practices. Supported by semantic technologies, RO-Crates are capable of capturing the relationships among all the components that participate in the ML workflow, making it easily shareable as well as reproducible. Due to the extensive use of RO-crates, this will be the preferred format, but alternative methods will be explored.

Frictionless Data is a progressive open-source framework proposed by the Open Knowledge Foundation for building data infrastructure: data management, data integration, data flows, etc. The approach for frictionless data is similar to RO-crates, containerizing not only the data but also the description of the data in JSON format. This metadata layer allows the description of any action required by the data, including preprocessing, curation processes, and relationships with software pieces. It provides a complete framework, including Python libraries to automate the process of creating a new frictionless data container.

Taking into account the interactions and recommendations from other EOSC-related projects (FAIR-Impact, FAIRCORE4EOSC), the most appropriate format will be selected, even exploring more alternatives. This analysis will be done during the next part of the project and the results described in D7.3 “Final report of Quality Assurance and data FAIRness”.

4.3.2 Tracking models: MLflow

MLflow³ is a platform to streamline ML development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models.

Key features of the tool are:

- **MLflow Tracking:** tracking experiments to record and compare parameters and results;

³ <https://github.com/mlflow/mlflow/>

- **MLflow Projects:** packaging ML code in a reusable, reproducible form in order to share with other data scientists or transfer to production;
- **MLflow Models:** managing and deploying models from a variety of ML libraries to a variety of model serving and inference platforms;
- **MLflow Model Registry:** providing a central model store to collaboratively manage the full lifecycle of an MLflow Model, including model versioning, stage transitions, and annotations.

In the context of AI4EOSC, a MLflow tracking server⁴ has been deployed primarily for experiment tracking. It is also capable of allowing users to self-register in MLflow⁵ via the project common AAI (EGI Check-In) and to manage permissions to their experiments and models with other users.

Apart from tracking the experiments, MLflow can be configured to capture and store any required information related to the ML models. It can be customised to gather information about the selected hyperparameters, the computing environment where the model has been processed, input and output data formats and software dependencies (Figure 1: MLflow: identifying package versions requirements.).

The screenshot displays the MLflow web interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'mlflow 2.10.2', 'Experiments', and 'Models'. Below this, the current run is identified as 'test_ml_project > run_02'. Key details include: Run ID: 3a0edd46bf4f41a981825d19acdec775, Date: 2024-02-09 14:10:11, Source: [icon] r, Duration: 1.2min, Status: FINISHED, and Lifecycle Sta[icon].

Underneath, there's a 'Description Edit' section with the text 'Car or Truck classifier for dummies'. A sidebar on the left lists various artifacts: Datasets, Parameters (7), Metrics (1), Tags (1), and Artifacts. The 'Artifacts' section is expanded, showing a file tree for 'model' containing 'data', 'MLmodel', 'conda.yaml', 'python_env.yaml', 'requirements.txt', 'accuracy_plot.png', and 'loss_plot.png'. The 'conda.yaml' file is selected, and its content is displayed in a code editor on the right. The code shows the full path, size (182B), channels (conda-forge), and dependencies (python=3.10.12, pip<=22.0.2, mlflow==2.10.2, cloudpickle==3.0.0, numpy==1.26.4, tensorflow==2.15.0.post1). The environment name is 'mlflow-env'.

Figure 1: MLflow: identifying package versions requirements.

⁴ <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>

⁵ <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/signup>

The use of MLflow to automatize the gathering of metadata and information about the workflow will be evaluated selecting at least one use case, which will be extended whenever the proper protocol and the automatization mechanisms were identified.

4.3.3 FAIR assessment tools

The FAIR principles were initially designed as a set of best practices for data and metadata publication. However, they are evolving to transcend the boundaries of data and serve as inspiration for other types of research objects. While most of the advances in FAIR assessment have focused on supporting data, efforts have been made to extend these principles to other research objects. For instance, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and its Working Group, titled FAIR Maturity WG, have developed a set of FAIR indicators based on the FAIR principles and sub-principles to measure the level of FAIRness adoption manually or automatically. Similarly, the FAIRsFAIR project [R13] has published similar approaches with a set of indicators. Building upon the RDA indicators, FAIR EVA (Evaluator, Validator, and Advisor) [R14] was implemented to not only assess the level of data FAIRness for different types of repositories but also provide advice on how to better adopt these principles. Its architecture, based on plugins, allows for adaptation to various types of repositories and data portals, enabling customization to provide different types of advice or interpret the list of tests according to specific needs. Furthermore, recent versions include systems to extend the predefined list of tests to include more specific tests focused on data. Figure 2: Snapshot of FAIR EVA assessment at DIGITAL.CSIC.

Figure 2: Snapshot of FAIR EVA assessment at DIGITAL.CSIC.

Since we are not only assessing data but also ML models workflows, the list of tests to be performed needs to be redefined. During the last AI4EOSC period, and in accordance with the work developed within this task, FAIR EVA will be updated to include specific tests for evaluating the FAIRness of the produced ML models. This may require extending the list of RDA indicators or even replacing them to better adapt to the AI reality. Furthermore, since FAIR EVA has already been integrated into the SQAaaS pipeline, it will be straightforward to update it automatically in the FAIR assessment. It includes an Application Programming Interface (API) to allow for machine-actionable assessments.

5. INFRASTRUCTURE: RESOURCES AND SERVICES FOR THE AI4EOSC PLATFORM

The architecture of the infrastructure and associated resources is shown in Figure 3. The endpoints of the services are shown. The diagram shows the endpoints of the services composing the current AI4EOSC platform; they include external SW components and services, as well as the ones developed by the project. The Confluence Wiki <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Resources+and+services> has a description and the details of all services.

Figure 3: AI4EOSC platform architecture. The endpoints of the services are shown.

5.1 AI4EOSC Platform services

The services below are deployed as a part of the AI4EOSC project. They are providing the necessary functionalities for the operation of the platform. Deliverables D4.2 [R3] and D5.2 [R4] have a detailed description of all the platform services.

5.1.1 PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning

PaaS Orchestration and Provisioning is a set of services, tools and scripts for automatic deployments of AI4EOSC components. The blueprints of the components are described in TOSCA templates together with a set of Ansibles roles for automatic configuration. The services consist of:

- PaaS Orchestrator providing a set of API's to create, monitor and manage deployments;
- The PaaS Dashboard is the GUI that enables the users to interact with PaaS Orchestrator;
- The Infrastructure manager (IM) automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring and update of virtualized infrastructures.

The services have the following endpoints:

- PaaS Orchestrator at INFN/BARI: <https://indigo-paas.cloud.ba.infn.it>
- IM at UPV: <https://im.egi.upv.es>
- PaaS Orchestrator at CNAF: <https://ai4eosc.cloud.cnaf.infn.it> (Backup instance)

5.1.2 AI4EOSC Dashboard

The AI4EOSC Dashboard is a web application that provides a visual interface for the user to access the platform resources in an easy and user-friendly way. The service is hosted here: <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>.

5.1.3 AI4EOSC Platform API

The Platform API provides a single endpoint to access all components of the platform. It hides the intrinsic complexity of the underlying technologies and provides users with a simple interface to use the services. Abstracting the underlying technology allows us more flexibility to change the technology used by any component without disrupting both users and other components. The service endpoint is hosted here: <https://api.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>.

5.1.4 AI4EOSC Workload management

The Workload Management System (WMS) in AI4EOSC leverages service mesh technologies to provide a unified, virtual, and distributed computing infrastructure across multiple cloud providers. This infrastructure facilitates the training of AI models and execution of other computationally intensive tasks.

The WMS is comprised of three key services:

- Nomad [R15]: This execution engine manages workload distribution across various compute nodes, ensuring efficient resource utilisation and timely completion of training processes.
- Consul [R16]: Consul acts as the central nervous system for service discovery and communication, enabling secure interaction between different tasks and services within the system.
- Traefik [R17]: As the gateway and load balancer, Traefik facilitates external access to services deployed on the WMS.

Two AI4EOSC clusters are currently operational: one at CSIC/IFCA and another at IISAS. The production cluster boasts significant computing resources, including:

- 694 CPU cores
- 1.5 TB disk space
- 1.9 TB RAM
- 33 GPUs

5.1.5 AI4EOSC AI as a service

For this project, the OSCAR [R18] platform is used to support the scalable inference of pre-trained AI models from the AI4EOSC marketplace: <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace>.

[OSCAR](#) is an open-source platform built on Kubernetes for event-driven data-processing of serverless applications packaged as Docker containers. To trigger the execution of these applications, OSCAR receives events from object-storage systems such as MinIO or dCache and creates the corresponding jobs that are executed on an elastic Kubernetes cluster for workload adaptation. Synchronous invocations of OSCAR services can also be performed for faster AI inference on an auto-scaled set of containers. The OSCAR endpoint is hosted here: <https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>.

5.1.6 AI4EOSC AI project templates service

To simplify the development of new AI modules by users and to facilitate integration of an AI model with the DEEPaaS API, Nextcloud, or other components, a set of software templates based on cookiecutters [R19] is provided. The platform offers a web service, <https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>, to create software projects based on these templates, where three options are currently available: a) the simple minimal template, a minimum of requirements to integrate the code b) the child module to retrain an existing AI module on user's own data c) the advanced module, which offers more options on how users can integrate their projects. Adding more templates is possible via GitHub pull requests.

5.1.7 MLflow Experiment tracking service

MLflow [R20] is an open-source platform to streamline ML development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models. MLflow Experiment tracking service is deployed for the AI4EOSC platform at: <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu> To simplify users' self-registration and managing of permissions of AI experiments, the mlflow-auth-gui service was added and available at <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/singup>,

where only members of vo.ai4eosc.eu are allowed to register for the MLflow experiment tracking.

5.1.8 AI4EOSC Container registry

Due to the change of the policies of Docker Hub, as well as providing better functionalities (vulnerability scanning, hosting private images with sensitive information), a container registry based on Harbor [R21] was deployed at LIP/INCD. The registry is integrated with EGI Check-in so that users can log into the service using their membership of AI4EOSC VO and manage the container images in the services. The service endpoint is hosted here: <https://registry.services.ai4eosc.eu> The training facilities will be implemented through a Workload Management System, which operates as a server-client cluster. This system will efficiently manage the distribution of workloads across multiple nodes, ensuring that the computational resources are utilized effectively and that the training process is completed in a timely manner. The user application will be encapsulated in containers based on Docker technology to ease the correct deployment inside the selected Compute client.

The Workload Management System in AI4EOSC is composed of three services: Nomad [R15] as execution engine, Consul [R16] for networking, and Traefik [R17] as the gateway and load balancer. Two clusters have already been deployed; one at CSIC/IFCA and the other at IISAS. The amount of resources of the current production cluster has; 694 CPU cores, 1.5 TB disk, 1.9 TB RAM and 33 GPUs. os.eu/. The docker images developed and built by the project, are being synchronised between this registry and Dockerhub.

5.1.9 AI4EOSC storage and data management service

Nextcloud [R22] is a file sync and share storage and data management service. It is a well known and proven solution that integrates well with the rest of the AI4EOSC platform. It's available at: <https://share.services.ai4eosc.eu/> and is connected to OpenIDC IdPs EGI-Checkin production instance.

5.1.10 AI4EOSC Monitoring service

As the AI4EOSC platform consists of many services, it is important to monitor the status of all services at a single place and notify providers in the case of incidents. The monitoring service is developed using Uptime open source tools and GitHub workflows. It's available at: <https://status.ai4eosc.eu/> and shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Uptime monitoring service for AI4EOSC platform.

5.2 AI4EOSC Cloud Infrastructure Providers

The compute resources needed for operating AI4EOSC services as well as for executing users' submitting jobs (AI training), are provided by five OpenStacks sites hosted by AI4EOSC partners:

- IFCA-LCG2 site at CSIC/IFCA: <https://portal.cloud.ifca.es/>
- IISAS-FedCloud site at IISAS: <https://cloud.ui.savba.sk/>
- NCG-INGRID-PT at LIP/INCD: <https://stratus.ncg.ingrid.pt/>
- INFN-CLOUD-BARI at INFN Bari: <https://cloud.recas.ba.infn.it>
- INFN-CLOUD-CNAF at INFN CNAF: <https://cloud-dashboard.cnaf.infn.it/>

All sites are integrated within the EGI Federated Cloud, thus integrated with the EGI Check-in and support “vo.ai4eosc.eu” VO. Only members of the VO “operators” group can log in and manage resources at the OpenStack sites.

5.3 AI4EOSC External services

The AI4EOSC platform is using the following external services that are necessary for completeness.

5.3.1 EGI Check-in and AI4EOSC virtual organisation

EGI Check-in is a proxy service that allows scientific communities to have a secure and controlled access to the resources and services in the EGI Federated infrastructure. It operates as a central hub that connects federated Identity Providers (IdPs) with EGI service providers. Its integration into the platform allows external usage by EGI users, in particular from the sister project iMagine [R23].

AI4EOSC providers, developers and end-users are managed in the “*vo.ai4eosc.eu*” Virtual Organisation (VO). For fine-grained access control and security improvements, three user groups have been created in the VO with different access rights, for example, end-users do not have access rights to low-level platform services. User support is provided via the support mailing list ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es or via AI4EOSC contact form on the AI4EOSC website.

5.3.2 Dynamic DNS

The Dynamic DNS service provides a unified, federation-wide Dynamic DNS support for VMs in EGI Cloud infrastructure. Users can register their chosen meaningful and memorable DNS hostnames in a given domain and assign public IPs to their servers.

Two domains have been added to the Dynamic DNS for AI4EOSC: the main domain “*cloud.ai4eosc.eu*” for AI4EOSC production services and the development domain “*dev.ai4eosc.eu*” for testing and development environment. As such, service providers can easily register hostnames for their services, for example the AI4EOSC dashboard <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace>, and assign them to the servers/VMs hosting the services.

5.3.3 EGI Secret stores

Some services in the AI4EOSC platform, such as the federated learning server, require a way to manage and share secrets securely. Therefore the EGI Secrets store service (<https://secrets.egi.eu/>) has been integrated with the AI4EOSC platform. Users can enter secret tokens via the dashboard, rotate or revoke them as needed.

6. FINAL REMARKS

This document describes the status of all activities of WP7. Part of the work has been the implementation and maintenance of documentation in Confluence Wiki pages: The Software Release guidelines that include the Software Quality

Assurance that SW components have to be verified in order to make part of the AI4OS stack release.

As part of this release procedure, Jira tickets are created for each SW component in order to track its evolution towards the release.

The list of Software components from WP4 and WP5 that compose the first AI4OS stack, are given in section 3.2. The releases in AI4EOSC are point in time releases, with all released versions at the time of the release.

The FAIR assessment status is described. In the framework of AI4EOSC, this assessment goes beyond data and metadata, it encompasses “*settings and hyperparameters*”, “*AI models*”, “*Software*” and “*workflows*”. Thus the State of the Art, tools and technologies are given in Sections 4.2 and 4.3.

The Software components developed within the project are deployed in the federated cloud infrastructure for usage by the users, and for execution of the use case applications. The platform has some missing components which are under development and not yet ready for deployment. These components will be deployed over the next periods upon their release.

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- [R6] PROV-O: The PROV Ontology: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>.
- [R7] World Wide Web Consortium (W3C): <https://www.w3.org/>.

- [R8] FAIR for Machine Learning (FAIR4ML) IG at RDA: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-machine-learning-fair4ml-ig>.
- [R9] FAIR-Impact: <https://fair-impact.eu/>.
- [R10] FAIRCORE4EOSC: <https://faircore4eosc.eu/>.
- [R11] Frictionless Data: <https://frictionlessdata.io/>.
- [R12] Research Object Crate (RO-Crate): <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>
- [R13] FAIRsFAIR project: <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>.
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- [R19] Cookiecutter, Better Project Templates, <https://cookiecutter.readthedocs.io/>.
- [R20] MLflow: A Machine Learning Lifecycle Platform, <https://mlflow.org/>.
- [R21] Harbor docker container registry: <https://goharbor.io/>.
- [R22] Nextcloud: <https://nextcloud.com/>.
- [R23] iImagine project: <https://www.egi.eu/project/imagine/>.

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CLI	Command Line Interface
DO	Digital Object
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IM	Infrastructure Manager
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
OSS	Open Source Software
PR	Pull Request
RDA	Research Data Alliance
SAST	Static Application Security Testing
SCM	Software Configuration Management
SQA	Software Quality Assurance
SvcQA	Service Quality Assurance
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service
VCS	Version Control System

ANNEX 1: SOFTWARE AND SERVICES QUALITY CRITERIA

This Annex details the Quality Criteria in the Confluence Wiki page⁶.

Annex 1.1: Mandatory Criteria

The following criteria are deemed mandatory for any SW component release.

1. Code Accessibility [QC.Acc]

- **[QC.Acc01]** Following the open-source model, the source code being produced **MUST** be open and publicly available to promote the adoption and augment the visibility of the software developments.
- **[QC.Acc02]** Source code **MUST** use a Version Control System (VCS).

2. Code Workflow [QC.Wor]

- **[QC.Wor01]** The main branch in the source code repository **MUST** maintain a working state version of the software component.

3. Code Management [QC.Man]

- **[QC.Man01]** An issue tracking system **MUST** be in place, it facilitates structured software development. Leveraging issues to track down both new enhancements and defects (bugs, documentation typos). (This criteria is adapted from the original baseline.)

4. Semantic Versioning [QC.Ver]

- **[QC.Ver01]** Semantic Versioning⁷ specification **SHOULD** be used for tagging the production releases. (This criteria is adapted from the original baseline.) This standard proposes a `.<MINOR>.<PATCH>` schema for tagging releases, where:
 - A MAJOR increment denotes incompatible changes breaking backwards compatibility (obsoletes components).
 - A MINOR increment denotes backwards-compatible features / functionalities.
 - A PATCH increment denotes backwards-compatible bug fixes.

⁶ <https://confluence.ifca.es/display/AI4/Software+and+Services+Quality+Assurance+%28SQA%29+guidelines>.

⁷ <https://semver.org>

5. Licensing [QC.Lic]

- **[QC.Lic01]** As open-source software, source code **MUST** adhere to an open-source licence to be freely used, modified and distributed by others. Non-licensed software is exclusive copyright by default. Licence **MUST** be compliant with the Open Source Definition⁸.
- **[QC.Lic01.1]** Licences **MUST** be physically present (e.g. as a LICENCE file) in the root of all the source code repositories related to the software component.

6. Documentation [QC.Doc]

- **[QC.Doc01]** Documentation **MUST** be treated as code.
- **[QC.Doc02]** Documentation is **RECOMMENDED** to use plain text format using a markup language, such as Markdown or reStructuredText. (This criteria is adapted from the original baseline.)
- **[QC.Doc03]** Documentation **MUST** be online and available in a documentation repository.
- **[QC.Doc04]** Documentation **MUST** be updated on new software versions involving any substantial or minimal change in the behaviour of the application.
- **[QC.Doc05]** Documentation **MUST** be updated whenever reported as inaccurate or unclear.
- **[QC.Doc06]** Documentation **MUST** be produced according to the target audience, varying according to the software component specification. The identified types of documentation and their **RECOMMENDED** content are:
 - **[QC.Doc06.1]** README file **MUST** be present:
 - A one-paragraph description of the application.
 - A "Getting Started" step-by-step description of how to get a development environment running (prerequisites, installation).
 - Automated test execution how-to.
 - Links to the external documentation below (production deployment, user guides).
 - Versioning specification.
 - Author list and contacts.
 - Acknowledgements.
 - **[QC.Doc06.5]** Developer, when applicable:
 - Private API documentation.
 - Structure and interfaces.
 - Build documentation.
 - **[QC.Doc06.6]** Deployment and Administration, when applicable:
 - Installation and configuration guides.

⁸ <https://opensource.org/osd>

- Service Reference Card, with the following RECOMMENDED content:
 - Brief functional description.
 - List of processes or daemons.
 - Init scripts and options.
 - List of configuration files, location and example or template.
 - Log files location and other useful audit information.
 - List of ports.
 - Service state information.
 - List of cron jobs.
- Security information.
- FAQs and troubleshooting.
- [QC.Doc06.7] User, when applicable:
 - Public API documentation.
 - Command Line Interface (CLI) reference.
 - Tutorials, HOWTO's.

7. Delivery [QC.Del]

- [QC.Del01] Production-ready code **MUST** be built as an artefact that can be efficiently executed on a system.
- [QC.Del02] The built artefact **MUST** be uploaded and registered into a public repository of such artefacts.

8. Deployment [QC.Dep]

- [QC.Dep01] Production-ready code **MUST** be deployed as a workable system with the minimal user or system administrator interaction leveraging software configuration management (SCM) tools.

Annex 1.2: Optional Criteria

For the **Bronze badge** mandatory QCA must be meet, plus:

Documentation [QC.Doc]:

- [QC.Doc06.2] CONTRIBUTING file **MUST** be present in order to communicate how external parties can contribute to the code.
- [QC.Doc06.3] A code of conduct (usually defined in a CODE_OF_CONDUCT file) **MUST** be present in order to establish the positive social attitudes expected within the community of code contributors.
- [QC.Doc01] Documentation **MUST** be treated as code,

- **[QC.Doc01.1]** Version controlled, it **MAY** reside in the same repository where the source code lies.
- **[QC.Doc02]** Documentation **MUST** use plain text format using a markup language, such as Markdown or reStructuredText.

For the **Silver badge**, the Bronze badge QCA must be met, plus:

Style [QC.Sty]

Code style requirements pursue the correct maintenance of the source code by the common agreement of a series of style conventions. These vary based on the programming language being used.

- **[QC.Sty01]** Each individual software product **MUST** comply with community-driven or de-facto code style standards for the programming languages being used.

Metadata [QC.Met]

Metadata for the software component provides a way to achieve its full identification, thus making software citation viable⁹. It allows the assignment of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and is key towards preservation, discovery, reuse, and attribution of the software component.

- **[QC.Met01]** A metadata file **SHOULD** exist alongside the code, under its VCS. The metadata file **SHOULD** be updated when needed, as is the case of a new version.

For the **Gold badge** the Silver badge QCA must be met, plus

Security [QC.Sec]

The security assessment is essential for any production Software. An effective implementation of the security requirements applies to every stage in the Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), especially effective at the source code level.

- **[QC.Sec02]** Source code **MUST** use automated linter tools to perform static application security testing (SAST)¹⁰ that flag common suspicious constructs that may cause a bug or lead to a security risk (e.g. inconsistent data structure sizes or unused resources).

⁹ Smith AM, Katz DS, Niemeyer KE, FORCE11 Software Citation Working Group. 2016. Software citation principles. PeerJ Computer Science 2:e86 <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.86>.

¹⁰ https://owasp.org/www-community/Source_Code_Analysis_Tools

